

MOLECULAR PHYSIOLOGY AND GENETICS

BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS OF ASBESTOS-RELATED DISEASES IN WORKERS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract

Introduction. The article reflects the impact of asbestos on human health due to the widespread use of asbestos-containing materials in the past in industrial and residential construction.

The aim of the study is to provide an analytical overview of the current state of biological markers of asbestos-related diseases, to show the risks of asbestos exposure to human health in production conditions, and to present current validated markers of mesothelioma and asbestosis.

Materials and methods. The study is based on an analysis of Ukrainian and foreign publications on the implementation of biological markers for the early detection of asbestos-related diseases in workers and the prospects for the use of new validated approaches and biological media for the early detection of mesothelioma and asbestosis.

Research results. The search for biomarkers is actively developing, as evidenced by the discovery of a number of promising candidates that could complement or replace SMRP. These include osteopontin, fibulin-3, HMGB1, and microRNA. This indicates a trend towards the creation of combined multi-marker panels that would increase the sensitivity and specificity of diagnosis and also have additional prognostic value, which is critical for the early detection of most cases of mesothelioma.

Conclusions. A review of the literature showed that the field of biochemical markers for asbestosis and mesothelioma is being actively studied and developed, especially in the context of the search for mesothelioma biomarkers. Although no single marker currently provides ideal diagnostic accuracy for both diseases, some require validation, but several are quite promising.

Keywords: asbestos, occupational exposure, biochemical markers. asbestos, mesothelioma.

Introduction

Elimination of asbestos-related diseases: WHO calls on all countries to completely ban the use of asbestos and to implement effective mechanisms for removing asbestos already present in buildings as part of national public health programmes. Today, there's a regulation in EU countries (Directive 2009/148/EC, amended by 2023/2668) that sets strict measures to minimise asbestos exposure during demolition, maintenance, or repair of buildings that contain asbestos. The current MPC in the air of the working area has been reduced tenfold: from 0.1 fibres/cm³ to 0.01 fibres/cm³ (average value for an 8-hour working day). The deadline for Member States to implement this new limit is 21 December 2025. A further reduction in the limit is planned by 21 December 2029 to 0.002 fibres/cm³ (if fine fibres are not measured) or maintenance at 0.01 fibres/cm³ (if all fibres are measured using electron microscopy).

An international scientific assessment of the impact of all types of asbestos on human health, conducted by the IARC and WHO, did not identify a threshold level below which asbestos exposure is safe and poses no risk to human health (no threshold for carcinogenicity).

However, despite bans in many developed countries, significant global exposure persists through mining, manufacturing and environmental contamination, putting millions of people at risk [1]. The World Health

Organisation (WHO) estimates that more than 100,000 deaths per year are related to asbestos [2].

The results of epidemiological studies show that there is a large amount of data obtained in different countries on the link between occupational exposure to asbestos and its mixtures (when inhaled into the human body) and the risk of developing asbestosis, pleural plaques, cancer of the larynx, bronchi, and lungs, ovarian cancer, and malignant mesothelioma (parietal pleura, peritoneum, pericardium). Most ASDs are fatal, and most ASDs are caused by asbestos in the lungs [1-5]. The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classifies asbestos as a known human carcinogen, also associated with lung, laryngeal, and ovarian cancer [3].

When asbestos fibres enter the respiratory tract, they settle in the lungs, causing a cascade of adverse effects, including the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), chromosome damage, mitotic disorders, gene mutations, and changes in growth factor signalling and apoptosis. These processes contribute to both fibrosis and carcinogenesis [4].

Given the long latency period characteristic of asbestos-related diseases, there is an urgent need for reliable early detection strategies. Biochemical markers that can be measured in readily available biological samples offer a potential avenue for identifying individuals at increased risk or detecting disease at a pre-clinical stage, thereby improving the prospects for effective treatment.

Research objective. The objective of this study is to analyse the current state of implementation and search for new biochemical markers for early detection of asbestos-related diseases in workers

Materials and methods. Analysis of specialized and scientific-methodological literature.

Object and methods of research.

The results of epidemiological studies show that there is a large amount of data obtained in different countries on the link between occupational exposure to asbestos and its mixtures (when inhaled into the human body) and the risk of developing asbestosis, pleural plaques, cancer of the larynx, bronchi and lungs, ovarian cancer, and malignant mesothelioma (of the parietal pleura, peritoneum, and pericardium [1-3]).

According to a number of researchers, the carcinogenic hazard of asbestos is not uniform and is determined by its type (chemical composition). A number of authors consider chrysotile asbestos to be the least hazardous to humans, which makes it possible to use it in industry with minimal risk to workers' health [2-8, 10-14]. The problem with identifying specific markers for asbestosis is that asbestos fibres themselves are not present in readily accessible biological fluids such as blood or urine; they are mainly localised in lung tissue [9-15]. Direct assessment of exposure often requires invasive procedures such as bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL). Therefore, research focuses on identifying 'response markers' that reflect changes in biological function caused by asbestos exposure, rather than the direct presence of fibres. These responses cover a spectrum of molecular changes, from oxidative stress to immune system activation.

Unlike mesothelioma, where the tumour itself produces specific molecules that can serve as markers, asbestosis is characterised by a non-tumour process of pulmonary fibrosis. This difference makes it difficult to identify markers with high specificity for asbestosis compared to other forms of pulmonary fibrosis or inflammatory conditions [9-13].

Asbestos exposure is a known inducer of oxidative stress in the lungs, leading to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that contribute to cell damage and fibrosis development.

In the context of asbestos exposure, several markers of oxidative stress have been investigated, including 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-oxo-dGuo) and 8-isoprostane PGF 2α (8-iso-PGF 2α). Elevated levels of 8-oxo-dGuo, a DNA adduct, in urine were associated with asbestos exposure [6]. Studies show that individuals with a history of asbestos exposure often exhibit higher levels of 8-OHdG in their biological samples. This suggests that 8-OHdG could potentially serve as a marker of exposure or early biological effect.

Although elevated levels of oxidative stress markers such as 8-OHdG indicate cell damage consistent with asbestos exposure, their diagnostic value for established asbestosis is limited by insufficient specificity. Elevated oxidative stress is a common feature of many lung diseases and even normal ageing, making it difficult to distinguish asbestosis from other conditions based on these markers alone.

There is evidence that asbestos exposure causes the release of hypermobile protein box 1 (HMGB1), a nuclear protein that is a powerful driver of chronic inflammatory processes leading to both fibrosis (characteristic of asbestosis) and carcinogenesis (relevant for mesothelioma and lung cancer) [7].

Studies have shown that individuals exposed to asbestos tend to have higher levels of HMGB1. In addition, increased levels of unacetylated HMGB1 in blood serum have been proposed as a potential biomarker of response to asbestos exposure [8].

HMGB1 appears to play a central role in the pathogenesis of asbestos-related diseases, including asbestosis. Although its elevated levels may indicate asbestos exposure and the presence of an inflammatory response that promotes fibrosis, HMGB1 is not specific to asbestosis and is also involved in the development of mesothelioma and other inflammatory conditions. Therefore, it may serve as a marker of exposure and potential risk rather than a definitive diagnostic marker for asbestosis.

Other potential markers include fibronectin and glycoprotein. It has been studied as a potential biomarker in individuals exposed to asbestos [6]. Its role in the fibrotic process in asbestosis makes it a logical candidate, but its specificity remains an issue, as it is involved in fibrosis of various origins and therefore requires further study of its role as a biomarker.

Several inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin 6 (IL-6) and interleukin 8 (IL-8), which play a key role in immune responses and inflammation, have been investigated as potential biomarkers of the body's response to asbestos exposure. Similarly, the chemokine RANTES (CCL5) has also been studied [6]. These markers reflect the inflammatory component of asbestosis, but are not specific to this disease. Mineralogical analysis of bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid is a more direct method of assessing asbestos exposure by measuring the number and type of asbestos bodies and fibres present in the lavage fluid. This analysis can detect higher concentrations of fibres in patients with asbestosis [8]. Although it is considered a reliable biomarker of past exposure and pulmonary burden, BAL is an invasive procedure requiring bronchoscopy and specialised laboratory expertise, limiting its routine use as a primary diagnostic tool [2].

Although biochemical markers can provide valuable information about the biological response to asbestos exposure, they currently play a more supportive role in the diagnosis of asbestosis. They can help identify individuals with significant exposure or understand the underlying pathological processes, but they are not yet sensitive or specific enough to serve as primary diagnostic criteria in most cases [6].

The established biochemical markers for mesothelioma are as follows:

Soluble mesothelin-related peptides (SMRP): Soluble mesothelin-related peptides (SMRP) are the most widely studied and only blood biomarker approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for mesothelioma. Mesothelin, a precursor protein with a molecular weight of 71 kDa, is physiologically cleaved into two

mature proteins: N-terminal megakaryocyte-potentiating factor (MPF) with a molecular weight of 31 kDa, secreted into the blood, and C-terminal glycosylated phosphatidylinositol-linked glycoprotein with a molecular weight of 40 kDa, which is bound to the plasma membrane. SMRP is released into the blood after further processing of the membrane-bound protein [8,13]. Serum SMRP levels are significantly elevated in patients with malignant mesothelioma compared to healthy individuals, individuals exposed to asbestos without mesothelioma, and individuals with benign asbestos-related diseases [13]. According to studies, the sensitivity of SMRP in the diagnosis of mesothelioma varies widely, from approximately 32% to 84%, while specificity is typically between 72% and 96%, depending on the control groups and thresholds used [8,15]. Sensitivity tends to be lower in the early stages of the disease and in non-epithelioid histological subtypes. SMRP plays a crucial role in monitoring patients diagnosed with epithelioid or biphasic mesothelioma for disease progression, response to treatment, and recurrence [8]. Elevated SMRP levels may indicate disease progression, while decreased levels may indicate response to therapy [15,16].

Other promising markers:

Osteopontin (OPN), an integrin-binding protein involved in various biological processes, including tumorigenesis, progression, and metastasis, is often found at elevated levels in the serum and plasma of patients with mesothelioma [6].

According to studies, the diagnostic sensitivity of OPN is approximately 65-78%, and specificity is approximately 81-86% in distinguishing mesothelioma from individuals exposed to asbestos [8]. However, its specificity tends to be lower when compared to benign pleural effusions or other diseases other than mesothelioma [16-19].

Several studies suggest that high OPN levels are associated with poor prognosis in patients with mesothelioma, indicating its potential as a prognostic marker [4,8].

Meta-analyses and comparative studies suggest that plasma OPN may demonstrate higher diagnostic accuracy compared to serum OPN, possibly due to thrombin degradation in peripheral blood [8,19].

Fibulin-3, an extracellular glycoprotein involved in the regulation of cell proliferation and migration, is another promising biomarker for mesothelioma, with elevated levels found in the blood and pleural effusions of patients [6].

Initial studies reported high diagnostic sensitivity (up to 90-97%) and specificity (approximately 95%) of fibulin-3 in blood plasma in distinguishing mesothelioma from individuals exposed to asbestos. However, subsequent validation studies have shown more heterogeneous results, with sensitivity ranging from 12.7% to 87% and specificity from 66% to 89% [9].

Fibulin-3 in pleural fluid has shown potential as a prognostic factor, with lower levels associated with longer survival in some studies [8]. High blood levels, on the other hand, may indicate a poorer prognosis [4,8].

High mobility group box 1 (HMGB1), a protein released during cell necrosis and involved in inflammation, is found at elevated levels in the serum of patients with mesothelioma [6].

Studies have shown that serum HMGB1 levels can reliably distinguish between patients with mesothelioma, individuals exposed to asbestos, and healthy control subjects. Notably, the hyperacetylated isoform of HMGB1 has demonstrated particularly high sensitivity (100%) and specificity (100%) in differentiating mesothelioma from individuals exposed to asbestos and healthy control subjects in some studies, outperforming other proposed biomarkers [9].

High HMGB1 levels are associated with poor prognosis in mesothelioma [6,9].

MicroRNAs (miRNAs), small non-coding RNA molecules that regulate gene expression, have shown altered expression patterns in patients with mesothelioma and individuals exposed to asbestos [4,14, 22]. A meta-analysis identified circulating miRNAs such as miR-126, miR-132-3p, and miR-103a-3p as promising diagnostic biomarkers for mesothelioma, with combined areas under the curve (AUC) indicating good diagnostic accuracy. Combining miRNAs with other markers, such as mesothelin, may further enhance diagnostic potential [9,10]. Certain miRNAs, such as miR-197-3p, have also been associated with prognosis in mesothelioma [8,15].

Immunohistochemical markers (tissue biopsy):

Although they are not biochemical markers in the traditional sense (soluble markers in fluids), immunohistochemical (IHC) markers play a crucial role in confirming the diagnosis of mesothelioma from tissue biopsies obtained through invasive procedures [9,16].

Calretinin: A highly sensitive mesothelial marker, positive in 80-100% of epithelioid mesotheliomas, but with lower sensitivity in sarcomatoid types (50-60%). It does not have ideal specificity, as it can be expressed in other malignant neoplasms [16].

Cytokeratin 5/6: Another widely used mesothelial marker with good sensitivity (51-100%) for epithelioid mesothelioma, but lower for sarcomatoid (13-29%). It can also be expressed in some squamous cell carcinomas [16].

WT1: A nuclear marker with reported sensitivity in the range of 70-100% for establishing the mesothelial lineage in epithelioid mesothelioma, but lower in sarcomatoid (10-45%). It may also be positive in some other carcinomas [16].

Podoplanin (D2-40): A membrane marker with high sensitivity (80-100%) for epithelioid mesothelioma. It is also a marker for lymphatic endothelium [16].

These and other IHC markers, including epithelial markers such as CEA and MOC-31, are commonly used in combination as an immunopanel to improve diagnostic accuracy and to differentiate mesothelioma from metastatic carcinomas and other pleural lesions [8].

Distinguishing between asbestosis and mesothelioma using biochemical markers:

Scientific reviews focus primarily on markers for detecting the effects of asbestos/asbestosis in general or specifically for mesothelioma [2-5]. Less attention is

paid to biochemical markers that would directly and definitively distinguish between established asbestosis and mesothelioma in individuals with a history of asbestos exposure. Some markers, such as HMGB1, are elevated in both conditions due to their common aetiology – asbestos exposure and involvement of inflammatory pathways. HMGB1 levels may be higher in mesothelioma in some cases, but this alone may not be sufficient for clear differentiation.

Soluble mesothelin-related peptides (SMRP) are generally considered to be more specific for mesothelioma and are not usually significantly elevated in isolated asbestosis [8]. Therefore, high SMRP levels in an individual exposed to asbestos and presenting with respiratory symptoms would raise suspicion of mesothelioma rather than asbestosis [13,17].

Osteopontin levels may be elevated in patients with asbestosis (especially those with pleural plaques and fibrosis) as well as in mesothelioma [16-21]. The degree of elevation may vary, with higher levels often seen in mesothelioma, but overlap is likely, limiting its use as a single marker for differentiation.

Prognostic and monitoring biochemical markers of mesothelioma:

Serum SMRP levels have shown potential in monitoring response to treatment and prognosis in mesothe-

lioma, with decreased levels potentially indicating improved survival. Higher baseline SMRP levels have been associated with poorer survival in some studies [8,22].

Osteopontin has also shown potential as a prognostic marker in mesothelioma. Several studies have reported that higher baseline serum or plasma osteopontin levels are associated with shorter overall survival [4, 8, 23].

Interestingly, fibrillin-3 levels in pleural fluid have been identified as an independent significant prognostic factor for survival in patients with mesothelioma, with lower levels correlating with longer survival [8]. High blood fibrillin-3 levels, on the other hand, may indicate a worse prognosis [4].

High levels of HMGB1 have been associated with poor prognosis in mesothelioma [4,8].

Certain microRNAs, such as miR-197-3p, have been associated with increased survival time in patients with mesothelioma, suggesting their potential as prognostic biomarkers [24, 25].

Longitudinal monitoring of SMRP levels and possibly other markers, such as osteopontin and fibulin-3, may provide valuable information for assessing tumour response to therapy and detecting disease progression or recurrence over time [8,28].

Table

Biochemical markers for the diagnosis of asbestosis and mesothelioma.

Marker	Sample type	Main clinical application	Sensitivity range (%)	Specificity range (%)	Main restrictions
Soluble mesothelin-related peptides (SMRP)	Serum, pleural fluid	Monitoring (Meso), Diagnostics (Mesotherapy)	32-84	72-96	Lower sensitivity in early stages and in non-epithelial mesothelioma
Osteopontin (OPN)	Serum, plasma	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy) Prognosis (Meso)	65-78	81-86	Lower specificity compared to benign pleural effusions and other diseases
Fibulin-3	plasma, Serum, pleural fluid	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy) Prognosis (Meso)	12.7-97	66-95	The sensitivity of the test in different studies requires further validation.
HMGB1	Serum	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy), Exposure (Asb)	72-100	80-100	Requires further validation, especially for the hyperacetylated isoform
microRNA (miRNAs)	Serum, plasma, Biological Tissue	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy), Prognosis (Meso)	Various	Various	Research is ongoing, requires validation as multimarker signatures
Mineralogical analysis (BAL)	BAL	Exposure (Asb), Asbestos Lung Burden	-	-	Invasive procedure
Calretinin (IGC)	Biological Tissue	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy)	50-100	60-98	Lower sensitivity in sarcomatoid mesothelioma, expressed

					in other cancers
Podoplanin (D2-40) (IGC)	Biological Tissue	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy)	80-100	High	Also stains lymphatic endothelium
ATG5	Blood	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy)	High	High	The information is preliminary and needs to be validated.
FLNA, FBLN1, TSP-1 (Proteomics)	Serum	Diagnostics (Mesotherapy)	High	High	New markers requiring validation

Note: Asb = Asbestos, Meso = Mesothelioma, IHC = Immunohistochemistry, BAL = Bronchoalveolar lavage. Sensitivity and specificity ranges are approximate and based on reviewed specimens.

Validation studies have identified filamin A (FLNA), fibulin 1 (FBLN1) and thrombospondin-1 (TSP-1) as promising diagnostic candidates that demonstrated high diagnostic value both individually and in combination for distinguishing mesothelioma from healthy control subjects, asbestos-exposed individuals, and patients with pleural plaques or asbestosis [29].

Autophagy-related protein 5 (ATG5), a factor involved in autophagy, has emerged as a new potential biomarker for the early detection of malignant pleural mesothelioma [27].

A study evaluating ATG5 levels in asbestos-exposed individuals, mesothelioma patients, and healthy control subjects found that ATG5 was most effective at distinguishing between asbestos-exposed individuals with and without mesothelioma.

Notably, ATG5 showed promise in detecting mesothelioma with high sensitivity and specificity in pre-diagnostic samples collected two years prior to clinical diagnosis [27].

Although miR-126 and mesothelin were identified as significant prognostic biomarkers in the same study, ATG5 stood out for its potential for early diagnosis [27].

Recent advances in proteomic technologies, such as analyses based on slowly dissociating modified aptamers (SOMAmer) and isobaric tags for relative and absolute quantification (iTRAQ) combined with liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), have facilitated the discovery of new panels of mesothelioma protein biomarkers [29].

Proteomic analysis based on SOMAmer identified a panel of 13 protein biomarkers that demonstrated high accuracy (approximately 92-99%) in detecting malignant mesothelioma in individuals exposed to asbestos, even detecting a significant proportion of the disease in its early (I/II) stages [28-30]. This panel included both inflammatory and proliferative proteins associated with asbestos-induced malignancies [31-34].

Using iTRAQ in combination with 2D-PLC-MS/MS, researchers identified 145 differentially expressed serum proteins between mesothelioma patients and healthy control subjects [29].

Further research into identifying specific biochemical markers that can effectively differentiate be-

tween asbestosis and mesothelioma, especially in individuals with a history of asbestos exposure who have respiratory symptoms, is warranted. A deeper understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying the development of asbestosis and mesothelioma is likely to lead to the discovery of additional new biomarkers and potential therapeutic targets.

Conclusions

1. A review of the literature showed that the field of biochemical markers for asbestosis and mesothelioma is being actively studied and developed, especially in the context of the search for mesothelioma biomarkers. Although no single marker currently provides ideal diagnostic accuracy for both diseases, some require validation, but several are quite promising.

2. Despite significant progress in the study of biomarkers for asbestos-related diseases, soluble mesothelin-related peptides (SMRP) remain the most established and only FDA-approved biomarker for monitoring mesothelioma.

3. The search for biomarkers is actively developing, as evidenced by the discovery of a number of promising candidates that could complement or replace SMRP. These include osteopontin, fibulin-3, HMGB1, and microRNA. This indicates a trend towards the creation of combined multi-marker panels that would increase the sensitivity and specificity of diagnosis and also have additional prognostic value, which is critical for the early detection of most cases of mesothelioma.

4. The analysis clearly shows a disproportion in the volume of research: the main focus is on mesothelioma. Research into specific biochemical markers of asbestosis itself is less extensive. Efforts in this direction are currently concentrated on indirect indicators, such as markers of asbestos exposure and markers of secondary processes — oxidative stress and fibrosis (e.g., HMGB1), which indicates an urgent need to discover more specific biomarkers for the early diagnosis of asbestosis itself.

References

1. Kazan-Allen E. Asbestos: The Global Perspective // *The Global Health Crisis of Asbestos: Lessons for the Future* / ed. by P. Bartrip, A. Frank. Routledge, 2015. 248 p.

2. WHO. Asbestos: elimination of asbestos-related diseases. Fact sheet No. 343. Updated March 2014.
3. IARC Monographs on the Identification of Carcinogenic Hazards to Humans. Arsenic, metals, fibres, and dusts. volume 100 C/ A review of human carcinogens, 2012, 527 p. ISBN-13 978-92-832-1320-8
4. Pass H.I., [et all] Biomarkers of mesothelioma: a review highlighting the contribution of the Early Detection Research Network. Pass H.I., Alimi M., Carbone M., Yang H., Goparaju C.M. // *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* – 2020.- Vol.29(12). - P.2524-2540. doi: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-20-0083.
5. Carbone M. Mesothelioma: Scientific clues for prevention, diagnosis, and therapy/ M. Carbone, P.S. Adusumilli, H.R. Alexander, Baas Jr, [et al] // *A Cancer Journal for Clinicians.* - 2018.- 69(5).- P. 402–429. DOI: [10.3322/caac.21572](https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21572)
6. van der Bij S. Urinary 8-oxodG, 8-iso-PGF2 α and C-reactive protein in relation to asbestos exposure / S. van der Bij, H. Koffijberg, V. Lenters et al. // *Particle and Fibre Toxicology.* – 2012. – Vol. 9, No. 1. – P. 28.
7. Yang H., [et al] Programmed cell death of mesothelioma cells is a key mechanism of HMGB1 release and asbestos-induced inflammation. / H. Yang, Z. Rivera, S. Jube, [et al] // *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS).* 107(28), 12611-12616. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.1001398107](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1001398107)
8. Ahmadzadeh T, Reid G, Kao S. Biomarkers in malignant pleural mesothelioma: current status and future directions. // *J Thorac Dis.* - 2018.- 10(Suppl 9) – P.S1003-S1007. doi: 10.21037/jtd.2018.04.31.
9. Sorino C, Mondoni M, Marchetti G, Agati S, Inchingolo R, Mei F, Flamini S, Lococo F, Feller-Kopman D. Pleural Mesothelioma: Advances in Blood and Pleural Biomarkers. // *J Clin Med.* -2023.- Vol.12(22). - P.7006. doi: 10.3390/jcm12227006.
10. Мехалік Н.П., Медведєв І. В. Лоїк В.Б. Оцінка ризиків азбестової експозиції та медичні наслідки для здоров'я людини. // *Collection of Scientific Papers «ЛОГОС»*, (February 2, 2024; Oxford, UK). 2024. С.153-156. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-02.02.2024.029>.
11. Кундієв Ю.И., Чернюк В.И., Басанец А.В., Остапенко Т.А. Клинико-гигиенические аспекты использования хризотилового асбеста в Украине. // *Довкілля та здоров'я.* 2011. №3 (58). С. 12-18.
12. Остапенко Т.А., Басанец А.В. Здоровье работников асбестоцементных предприятий Украины. *Медицина Кыргызстана.* 2014, Вып. 4. С. 104-112.
13. Марченко М.Л., Варивончик Д.В. Молекулярні механізми патогенезу злоякісної мезотеліоми, обумовленої експозицією азбестом та вірусом SV-40. // *Український журнал з проблем медицини праці.* 2013. № 1. С.57-70. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33573/ujoh2013.01.057>.
14. Gao Q. The diagnostic value of circulating microRNAs for malignant pleural mesothelioma: a systematic review and meta-analysis / Q. Gao, X. Lin, J. Feng et al. // *Disease Markers.* – 2021. – Vol. 2021. – Art. ID 6638058. – 12 p.
15. Cavalleri T. Circulating microRNAs as a tool for early diagnosis of malignant mesothelioma / T. Cavalleri, C. Angelici, C. Bertazzi et al. // *Occupational and Environmental Medicine.* – 2017. – Vol. 74, No. 1. – P. 28–36.
16. Husain A. N. Guidelines for Pathologic Diagnosis of Malignant Mesothelioma: 2017 Update of the Consensus Statement from the International Mesothelioma Interest Group / A. N. Husain, T. V. Colby, N. G. Ordóñez et al. // *Archives of Pathology & Laboratory Medicine.* – 2018. – Vol. 142, No. 1. – P. 89–108. DOI: [10.5858/arpa.2017-0214-CP](https://doi.org/10.5858/arpa.2017-0214-CP)
17. Robinson B. W. S, [et all] Mesothelin-family proteins and diagnosis of mesothelioma/ Robinson B. W. S, Jenette Creaney, Richard Lake, A. Nowak, [et all] // Lancet.- 2003.- 362(9396).-P.1612-6. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(03)14794-0.
18. Wolff H. Asbestos, asbestosis, and cancer: the Helsinki criteria for diagnosis and attribution 2014: recommendations / H. Wolff, T. Vehmas, P. Oksa et al. // *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health.* – 2015. – Vol. 41, No. 1. – P. 5–15.
19. Hollevoet K. The diagnostic value of soluble mesothelin-related peptides for malignant pleural mesothelioma: a meta-analysis / K. Hollevoet, J. P. van Meerbeeck [et al.] // *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine.* – 2012. – Vol. 185, No. 8. – P. 869–878.
20. Moncivais, K., Ph.D. (n.d.). Mesothelioma Blood Tests | MESOMARK, SMRPs & More. Mesothelioma.com. Retrieved from <https://www.mesothelioma.com/mesothelioma/diagnosis/biomarkers-blood-tests/> (Accessed May 13, 2025).
21. Nash A, Firth T, Creaney J. New Markers for Management of Mesothelioma. // *Semin Respir Crit Care Med.* -2023 – Vol.44(4), - P.491-501. doi: 10.1055/s-0043-1769097.
22. Creaney J. Serum and pleural fluid biomarkers for mesothelioma / J. Creaney, B. W. Robinson // *Current Opinion in Pulmonary Medicine.* – 2017. – Vol. 23, No. 4. – P. 344–348.
23. Chen Z, Gaudino G, Pass HI, Carbone M, Yang H. Diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers for malignant mesothelioma: an update. // *Transl Lung Cancer Res.* 2017 –Vol.29, №6(3) – P.259-269. doi: 10.21037/tlcr.2017.06.07.
24. Micocci L, Akhtar MM, Olivieri F, Rippo MR, Procopio AD. Diagnostic value of microRNAs in asbestos exposure and malignant mesothelioma: 1 a systematic review and qualitative meta-analysis. // *Oncotarget.* - Vol.27(36). - P.58606-58637. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.9686.
25. Mukhopadhyay D., Cocco P., Orrù S., Cherchi R., De Matteis S. The role of MicroRNAs as early biomarkers of asbestos-related lung cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis. // *Pulmonology.* -2025.- Vol.31(1). - P.2416792. doi: 10.1016/j.pulmoe.2024.02.002.
26. Tomassetti M, Monaco F, Strogovets O, Volpini L, Valentino M, Amati M, Neuzil J, Santarelli L. ATG5 as biomarker for malignant mesothelioma early detection. // *BMC Res Notes.* - 2023. - Vol. 24;16(1). - P. 61. doi: 10.1186/s13104-023-06330-1.

27. Bunting, K. Mesothelioma Blood Tests: MESOMARK & Other Biomarkers. Asbestos.com. Retrieved from <https://www.asbestos.com/mesothelioma/blood-test/> (Accessed May 13, 2025).
28. Arnold D.T., De Fonseca D., Hamilton F.W., Rahman N.M., Maskell N.A. Prognostication and monitoring of mesothelioma using biomarkers: a systematic review. // *Br J Cancer*. -2017.- Vol.116(6). - P.731-741. doi: 10.1038/bjc.2017.22. Epub 2017 Feb 7.
29. Mesaros C., Worth A.J., Snyder N.W., Christofidou-Solomidou M., Vachani A., Albelda S.M., Blair I.A. Bioanalytical techniques for detecting biomarkers of response to human asbestos exposure.// *Bioanalysis*. - 2015 Vol.7(9).-P.1157-1173. doi: 10.4155/bio.15.53.
30. Döngel İ., Akbaş A., Benli İ., Bayram M. Comparison of serum biochemical markers in patients with mesothelioma and pleural plaques versus healthy individuals exposed to environmental asbestos. // *Türk I Gogus Kalp Damar Cerrahisi Derg*. 2019-Vol.28;27(3).- P.374-380. doi: 10.5606/tgkdc.dergisi.2019.17557
31. Foddìs R., Bonotti A., Monaco F., Gaudino G., Ferrante L., Caciagli L., Cariti A., Mutti S., Dattrino P., Migliore M., Cavallesco G., Fontana A.. Biomarkers in the prevention and follow-up of workers exposed to asbestos.// *J. Thorac Dis*.- 2018.-Vol.10(Suppl 2).- P.S360-S368. doi: 10.21037/jtd.2018.01.73.
32. Sun J.H., Weinblatt A., Pass H.I. Diagnosis and prognosis—review of biomarkers for mesothelioma.// *Ann Transl Med*.- 2017.- Vol.5(11).-P.244. doi: 10.21037/atm.2017.06.60.
- Lagniau S., Lamote K., van Meerbeeck J.P., Vermaelen K.Y. Biomarkers for early diagnosis of malignant mesothelioma: Do we need another moonshot? // *Oncotarget*. - 2017.- Vol. 8(32). P. 53751-53762. doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.17910.
33. Matsuzaki H, Kumagai-Takei N, Lee S, Maeda M, Sada N, Hatayama T, Yamamoto S, Ikeda M, Yoshitome K, Min Y, Nishimura Y, Otsuki T. Search for biomarkers of asbestos exposure and asbestos-induced cancers in investigations of the immunological effects of asbestos.// *Environ Health Prev Med*.- 2017.- Vol.22.- P 53. doi: 10.1186/s12199-017-0661-4.
34. Ostroff, R. M. (2012). Biomarkers detected mesothelioma after asbestos exposure.// Healio. 2012 Retrieved from https://www.healio.com/news/hematology-oncology/20121017/hot1012ostrof_10_3928_1081_597x_20121001_10 (Accessed May 13, 2025).